

Synthesis of New Local Anaesthetics. Part VI

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Diethylaminoacetyl-2-amino-4-phenyl-, -4-*p*-chlorophenyl-, -4-*p*-bromophenyl-, -4-methyl- and piperidinoacetyl-2-amino-4-*p*-bromophenyl-thiazoles have been synthesised and their local anaesthetic activities tested. The hydrochloride of diethylaminoacetyl-2-amino-4-*p*-chlorophenylthiazole has been found to be the most potent amongst the compounds described.

In continuation of our previous work (Bhargava *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1957, **34**, 42; 1960, **37**, 241, 314), 2-amino-4-phenyl-, -4-*p*-chlorophenyl-, -4-*p*-bromophenyl- and -4-methyl- thiazoles were prepared and were condensed with chloroacetyl chloride to obtain the corresponding chloroacetyl-amino compounds. These chloroacetyl-amino derivatives were further condensed with a secondary amine, like diethylamine and piperidine. The hydrochlorides of these bases have been prepared and their local anaesthetic activities tested by frog's sciatic plexus method.

A study of the pharmacological screening (Bulbring and Wajda, *J. Pharmacol. & Exp. Therap.*, 1945, **85**, 78) shows that the hydrochlorides of diethylaminoacetyl-2-amino-4-*p*-chlorophenyl-, -4-*p*-bromophenyl- and piperidinoacetyl-2-amino-4-*p*-bromophenyl-thiazoles are active compounds, and amongst these, the first compound is the most potent.

It is observed that an extra halogen atom in *para* position in phenyl nucleus enhances the local anaesthetic activity.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-Amino-4-substituted Thiazoles.—2-Amino-4-phenyl-, -4-*p*-chlorophenyl-, -4-*p*-bromophenyl- (m.p. 180°), and -4-methyl-thiazoles were prepared according to the methods of Dodson and King (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 2242) and Bhargava *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

*Chloroacetyl-2-amino-4-*p*-bromophenylthiazole.*—2-Amino-4-*p*-bromophenylthiazole (8 g.), dissolved in pure dry benzene (30 c.c.), was taken in a round bottomed flask and chloroacetyl chloride (5 c.c.), dissolved in pure dry benzene (15 c.c.), was gradually added to it. The reaction mixture was warmed at 70° on a water-bath for 1.5 hours. Benzene was distilled. The residue was first washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and then with water, and dried. The product was crystallised from ethanol as a brown solid, m.p. 145°, yield 6g. (Found: S, 9.62. $C_{11}H_9ON_2BrClS$ requires S, 9.65%).

Similarly chloroacetyl derivatives of 2-amino-4-*p*-chlorophenyl- and -4-methyl-thiazoles were obtained (Bhargava *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

Diethylaminoacetyl-2-amino-4-phenylthiazole.—To chloroacetyl-2-amino-4-phenylthiazole (5 g.), dissolved in ethanol (50 c.c.), diethylamine (2 c.c.) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 5 hours at 50°. Ethanol and unchanged diethylamine were recovered by distillation; the residue was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water. The product was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 80°. (Found: S, 10.98. $C_{15}H_{19}ON_3S$ requires S, 11.07%).

Similarly diethylaminoacetyl and piperidinoacetyl derivatives of other 2-aminothiazoles were prepared. Their properties and analytical data are reported in Table I.

The hydrochlorides of these bases were prepared as usual. Their properties and analytical data are mentioned in Table I.

TABLE I

Diethylaminoacetyl- and piperidinoacetyl-2-aminothiazoles and their hydrochlorides.

No.	* Compounds.	Acetyl-2-aminothiazoles.		Hydrochlorides.				
		M. P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.		M. P.	% Chlorine.	
				Found.	Calc.		Found.	Calc.
1.	Da-A-4-phenyl-T	80°	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ ON ₂ S	10.98	11.07	120°	10.87	10.90
2.	Da-A-4- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-T	65°	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ ON ₂ ClS	9.74	9.89	130°	9.79	9.86
3.	Da-A-4- <i>p</i> -bromophenyl-T	172°	C ₁₅ H ₁₈ ON ₂ BrS	8.54	8.69	160°	8.72	8.77
4.	Pa-A-4- <i>p</i> -bromophenyl-T	170°	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ ON ₂ BrS	8.62	8.42	155°	8.48	8.52
5.	Da-A-4-methyl-T	98°	C ₁₀ H ₁₇ ON ₂ S	14.15	14.09	215°	13.36	13.47

* Da denotes diethylaminoacetyl, A denotes 2-amino, Pa denotes piperidinoacetyl, and T, thiazole.

Pharmacological Test : Plexus Anaesthesia in Frogs.—The hydrochlorides of diethylaminoacetyl- and piperidinoacetyl-2-amino-4-substituted thiazoles were screened for local anaesthetic activity by frog's sciatic plexus test in the month of May. Two frogs were tested for each compound in 0.1% and 0.2% concentration and the time taken by a given concentration of a local anesthetic to fail to provoke withdrawal of foot was recorded, and compared with that of procaine hydrochloride as a standard substance. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Local anaesthetic activity of the compounds.

No.	Hydrochlorides of	With 0.1 % soln. for onset of anaesthesia in		With 0.2 % soln. for onset of anaesthesia in	
		0.1N-HCL	0.2N-HCL	0.1N-HCL	0.2N-HCL
1.	Da-A-4-phenyl-T	15 mins.	20 mins.	11 mins.	15 mins.
2.	Da-A-4- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-T	11	15	7	10
3.	Da-A-4- <i>p</i> -bromophenyl-T	15	21	12	15
4.	Pa-A-4- <i>p</i> -bromophenyl-T	13	16	10	12
5.	Da-A-4-methyl-T	17	21	15	18
6.	Procaine	15	20	14	17

The study of the pharmacological screening shows that the hydrochloride of diethylaminoacetyl-2-amino-4-*p*-chlorophenylthiazole has the highest local anaesthetic activity among the present compounds and requires less time for the onset of anaesthesia than the standard substance, procaine hydrochloride.

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